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Start-up innovation and growth in health-related industries

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Abstract. Start-ups are recognised among the key contributors to the creation of patient-centric, digitalised and connected solutions leading to the so-called Healthcare 5.0. However, they have to tackle the intrinsic liabilities of newness. This study investigates the innovation strategy and growth patterns of start-ups that introduce new products, services or integrated solutions to meet social needs, whose main purpose is to improve health conditions and the well-being of people with advanced technologies and dedicated services. We conducted a multiple case study research by selecting four start-ups incubated in UPTEC, the science and technology park of the University of Porto in Portugal. Findings show that healthcare start-ups follow either “qualitative” (in terms of employees and mix of competences) or “quantitative” (in terms of financial resources, i.e. funds and revenues) growth patterns, and accordingly ways of leveraging the interconnections of the innovation ecosystem they belong to.

Keywords: Company growth, Start-ups, Locus of innovation, Intermediary, Healthcare industry

1 Introduction

The healthcare industry and, in general, industries aimed at enhancing people well-being and health conditions, need to continuously pursue improvements to respond to customers' requirements. Especially with the ageing population trends and the pandemic outbreak, organisations are increasingly challenged to rethink their innovation strategies and the overall innovation ecosystem structure [1]. These challenges also entail the creation of patient-centric, digitalised and connected solutions that are changing the landscape of healthcare offerings in the so-called Healthcare 5.0, integrating the principles and applications of Industry 4.0 with the further customisation of care, therapeutics and diagnostics to patients and professionals [2,3]. In this sense, start-ups are recognised among the key contributors to the innovation and unlocking of new market spaces in established and highly competitive industries as health-related ones [4]. The early-stage ventures mainly focus on transformative solutions for advanced care, evidence-based and outcomes-driven treatment approaches and technology-enabling treatments for specific health conditions [2,4].

Conversely, innovative start-ups have to tackle the intrinsic liabilities of newness and smallness, with a lack of resources to define the routines to effectively implement their strategy and compete with incumbent firms [5,6]. To overcome these liabilities and achieve a better innovation performance (especially in terms of wider outcomes), these firms can rely on sourcing external resources and knowledge spillovers, especially in knowledge-intensive industries [7].

Along the emerging and clinical development stages, new healthcare ventures need to rely on grants, investments, and multiple venture capital rounds, as well as possible partnerships with larger organisations along different value chain tiers [2]. Conversely, investors are reluctant to invest in new technologies and business models that show more uncertainty and longer time horizons to become profitable, especially in highly knowledge-intensive industries as healthcare [8].

Further research should explore the new venture strategies to create new market spaces, facing different customer expectations and hybrid approaches, including both digital solutions and on-premise (or home) services [4]. Few studies investigated the construction of new firms' innovation and their knowledge-sharing patterns within their ecosystem in the field of health technology start-ups [9]. These could be considered by studying the different choices of external knowledge sourcing in new ventures and how different sources may play a particular role [7].

This research aims to study the innovation strategy and growth patterns of start-ups that introduce new products, services or integrated solutions to meet social needs, whose main purpose is to improve health conditions and the well-being of people with advanced technologies and dedicated services. The research question guiding the investigation was formulated as follows: *How do start-ups in health-related industries develop in terms of company growth and innovation strategy patterns?*

We conducted a multiple case study research by selecting four start-ups incubated in UPTEC, the science and technology park of the University of Porto in Portugal. This research setting allowed us to investigate the innovation patterns of start-ups, also

considering the collaboration with an innovation intermediary as the incubator, and its role in specific development patterns.

2 Theoretical background

Despite their potential, many new firms fail in the early stages of their life and few grow to medium size, with the small size of start-ups entailing a limited scope for investing in research and development (R&D) processes and a lack of resources for structuring normal operative activities [10]. Starting a new business entails the creation of an innovative product or service – and sometimes seeking a new market – in a context of extreme uncertainty and high-competitive pressure [11].

Start-ups should opt for a business model that is scalable, repeatable in time and profitable in terms of return on investments, with a customer base easy to increase [12]. In the case of early stages ventures, it is difficult to accurately measure growth as in the case of incumbents, or rely on metrics such as customers, profits, and turnover before the start-up has reached sustainability [13]. A definition of growth should investigate not only more traditional metrics such as sales and number of customers, but also non-financial dimensions such as skills and capabilities, also considering that in the early stages of start-ups the financial data are not readily available [10,13]. This phenomenon is known as the liability of newness, according to which start-ups' mortality rates are highest in the earliest years [14]. For example, the evolution of a start-ups' life cycle is characterised by multiple stages, the most critical of which is probably represented by the so-called “valley of death” [15]: often, start-ups fail to generate revenues soon after they have received funds/resources from third parties such as venture capitalists, thus making them fail. Important factors to overcome the liabilities of smallness and newness of start-ups are the openness to external knowledge sources [16] and the creation of purposeful business relationships for pursuing innovation [11]. Innovative start-ups often try to leverage the relationships within the innovation ecosystem that is bounded at the local, regional or national level [6]. Extant studies have addressed the innovation ecosystem by taking the perspective of the incumbent [e.g. 17], comparing the performance of the actors (e.g. university spin-offs or innovative start-ups) within an innovation ecosystem [18], and also looking at the role that different actors play across the different stages of the innovation process [19].

Unfortunately, start-ups do not often know how to identify and exploit the connectedness with their innovation environment and need support in promoting innovation and entrepreneurship [20]. It has been demonstrated that the context of open innovation offered by intermediaries, such as incubators and science and technology parks, can affect the successful growth of start-ups participating in business development programmes [10, 16]. In particular, increasing attention has been given to the role of incubators for start-ups from both a transactional and a relational form of support [21]. However, little is known about how start-ups leverage different types of support and the different paths they may follow for their growth and, overall, what growth means for a start-up. In fact, extant studies have started distinguishing between quantitative growth goals and qualitative growth ones, also relating their pursuit to

organisational resilience [22]. Therefore, understanding how start-ups leverage an innovation ecosystem, or even different networks, for different growth paths may represent an interesting field of research.

3 Methodology

With the aim of performing a contextualised investigation of a contemporary phenomenon and its complexity [23,24], we conducted a multiple case study research. We purposefully chose companies based on the criteria of 1) being a start-up, i.e., a new venture recently founded (at the time of the study) to create a new solution addressing unmet needs in a market, with the potential of growing and scaling their business; 2) being established with the explicit aim of introducing a new product, service, technology or integrated solution to enhance people's health conditions and well-being, thus with the willingness of entering a health-related industry; 3) whose solutions reflect the Healthcare 5.0 principles of integrating smart and advanced technologies with personalised offerings for health conditions. In addition, we opted for having homogeneity from a socio-economic perspective, with cases belonging to the same innovation ecosystem. We thus focused on four start-ups developing healthcare solutions and being incubated in UPTEC, the science and technology park of the University of Porto in Portugal.

UPTEC is a business incubator that aims to foster the creation and development of business projects in the arts, sciences and technologies, through sharing knowledge between the university and the market. This incubator provides its incubated start-ups with not only physical spaces and laboratories where they can work. A key added-value service is also the networking, mainly with Porto University, investors and other incubated start-ups. UPTEC organises seminars and mentoring activities and provides, through its partners, different kinds of business services at discount prices, including legal advice, cloud services, intellectual property and communication services.

We also selected companies with the criteria of heterogeneity in terms of types of solutions, industries, and locus of innovation. Table 1 provides an overview of the four cases.

Table 1. Overview of case studies.

	Solution / Industry	Locus of innovation	Foundation year	Incubation year
Case A	AI in healthcare	Continuous improvement of the technology for diagnostics in digestive healthcare	2021	2021
Case B	AI in well-being	Starting from a tool for tracking physical exercise for sports people, they are improving the technology to provide the service to professional trainers	2019	2019
Case C	Sustainable leather	Starting from the technology of human skin reconstruction, they use the same technology for treating animal skin to be used in the leather sector	2020	2020
Case D	Device for health status assessment	Starting from technologies for strength assessment, they changed the use to elderly fragility assessment	2018	2018

3.1 Data collection

Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. Primary sources were semi-structured interviews with the start-ups' founder teams and part of the UPTEC staff involved in the business development, investments and entrepreneurship programmes. To assure coherence and consistency, a standard interview protocol was developed based on the literature review and prior to the data gathering to guide and check it. The interview protocol included both semi-structured and open-ended questions and was organised in the following sections:

- General description of the company history, main motivations driving the business idea and the innovative solution;
- Innovation strategy: drivers, main focus and evolutions, external sources of knowledge involved in the development process;
- Growth: most significant indicators of growth for the start-ups from the foundation;
- Relationship with incubator UPTEC: year of incubation, type of services and resources adopted, relationships within the innovation ecosystem, impacts of networks on company growth and innovation strategy.

Each interview lasted between 35 and 60 minutes. All interviews were recorded and transcribed. Transcriptions of interviews were then triangulated with publicly available and private data from the UPTEC website, press reviews, official companies' documents such as websites and archival documents provided by informants, observations taken during the two months visiting period of the first and the second authors, participation in events organised by UPTEC with tenant start-ups, with moments dedicated to pitches and storytelling by the incubated companies.

3.2 Data analysis

Data collected were further analysed following a two-step procedure of within- and cross-case analysis [24]. After depicting the growth and innovation strategy of each start-up and their experience of incubation, the cross-case analysis allowed thus to identify, compare and contrast the innovation patterns and types of growth characterising the four healthcare start-ups. The patterns were also defined considering the role of the incubator and the innovation ecosystem the start-ups are leveraging in their growth.

4 Results

4.1 Within-case analysis results

The four case studies are here briefly described.

Case A. The start-up was founded in 2021 and it developed an artificial intelligence (AI)-based solution for diagnostic and therapeutic procedures to increase diagnostic accuracy in digestive healthcare. The business idea was born from the PhD thesis of one of the entrepreneurs and it took two years to be developed.

The innovation strategy is mainly internally based (from the R&D area) and the ideas emerge from the hospital's daily life, in particular from the many hospitals the company has as partners, also from abroad.

For the manager, the most important benefit provided by the incubator to the company is the networking with the University of Porto, *“because we were born from the Faculty of Medicine and the Faculty of Engineering, so the proximity is really important. [...] We currently have engineering students collaborating with our enterprise. So, I think UPTEC [...] is part of the same culture, we basically leverage our academic background and try to make it profitable. [...] Also, we used the University of Porto innovation for submitting our patents and, in terms of intellectual property, University of Porto was also instrumental for us.”*

On the contrary, the founder does not think that the physical proximity with other start-ups is an important benefit.

The company has grown a lot and it is almost ready to leave the incubator. In terms of employees, it has grown from 8 founders to about 30 employees.

Case B. The start-up develops a technology that tracks physical exercises with AI. It was born in 2019, and immediately incubated in UPTEC. Initiated by 4 founders, later two of them left and they hired two new employees. At the beginning, the company raised without external funding. Currently, they do not have partners and they leverage their customers' knowledge to train the AI technology: they just ask personal trainers and physical education teachers what they can improve, in particular adding new physical exercises in the software. In this way, they decided to change consumer targets, moving from final consumers to this kind of professional people.

One dimension of their growth can also be measured in the number of exercises available in the software, because the AI allows to add a new specific exercise for a specific client. They started from about 20 exercises developed in 3-4 years and the goal is to reach 100-200 exercises in this year.

Regarding UPTEC, they use spaces, mentorship, investorship and networking with other entrepreneurs.

Case C. The company operates in the field of bioproduction of leather goods, they reconstruct animal skin for fashion uses. The idea of the founders came, also in this case, from a PhD where they learnt how to reconstruct human skin and they decided to apply this technique to animals in order to save their lives.

The business idea was born in 2018 and the company was founded in 2020, six months later when they were incubated in UPTEC. Currently, the company is still not ready to sell, and the founders are fundraising again while concentrating on hiring new employees.

Their partners are veterinary and zoological centres where they get the skin samples to reconstruct, but the ideas came entirely from the company. Part of their activities is in partnership, while the market orders are managed internally.

The company has a strong relationship with UPTEC network, not only in using discounts for services but mainly in the relationship with other incubated companies. One of the interviewee also pointed out that one of the fundraising that they got was possible just since they were incubated *“because for this particular call [...] you could only propose your company if you were incubated in a centre and it was actually the centre that makes the application for you”*.

Case D. The company is developing a solution for assessing the nutritional and physical status of people based on muscles and body composition. The final idea came in 2019 after two years in which they developed similar technologies but for different applications with the partnership of UPTEC and the University of Porto.

Their innovation strategy is mainly driven by market and funding opportunities. The start-up is in the take-off phase, in the next months they expect to start selling on the market, having an exponential growth in revenues after a period in which they have been mostly focused on small sales and research. They started with two founders and now it has 4 employees and they plan to arrive at 12 or 14 in the next 3-4 months and they are also moving into their own building, keeping just a small office in the UPTEC building to exploit its training activities, fundraising opportunities and networking with other start-ups.

4.2 Cross-case analysis results

Results of the cross-case analysis reveal that start-ups are pursuing different types of growth according to the development patterns of their innovative solutions, but also ways of leveraging the innovation networks.

Specifically, the innovation patterns can be characterised in terms of the main driver, i.e. the starting point of innovation, and the locus of innovation, i.e. the focus of the innovation after a timespan of development.

Case A and D pursued a strategy of *focalisation*, i.e. maintaining the locus of innovation as the original driver. Specifically, Case A's innovative efforts have always addressed the technology, by integrating medical and IT competences to evolve the technical parts of the solution. As the founder said: "*as we are doctors, we know what kind of solutions can help in our daily life working in the hospital*".

Case D mainly innovated the use of its solution, by expanding the possible use cases in terms of health conditions and the type of patients to be served with their innovative solution, as the manager said: "*the only thing we had before was [...] something that could be used, the thing was using it in an effective way to bring value for the people*".

Conversely, Case B and C pursued a strategy of *shift*, i.e. changing from an initial driver of innovation to a different locus of innovation during their development path. Specifically, Case B's innovation maintained the initial use case, i.e. the fitness area, and the innovation efforts were mainly towards the technology, i.e. evolving its innovative solution from an app to an AI-based platform. Case C's innovation path shifted in the complementary direction, i.e. starting from an innovative process of extracting cells from a technological perspective, while mainly focusing on the changes in terms of possible uses and thus exploitation in a different biotechnology application "*because we already knew how to reconstruct in laboratory the human skin, we decided to go for the animal skin*" the founder says.

Interestingly, the two cases that pursued a strategy of focalisation, i.e. Case A and D, are the ones that mainly focused on growing in terms of funds and revenues, which we can operationalise as "quantitative growth" as it is mainly aimed at increasing the financial resources. Moreover, both Case A and D demonstrated being able to leverage the network of investors of UPTEC, but also the network of external sources of knowledge and resources outside the UPTEC direct networks. As highlighted by the founder of Case D, "*So we are completely open, we work a lot with subcontractors as soon as we have funding and that's the thing, we are trying to innovate based on that and working with the environment*". This has allowed them to maximise raising funds and starting revenues: "*we expect to have a growth [...], cause until now we have been mostly focused on small sales, researches and things like that and now it's the time to bring the product and the money. We had such a small amount of sales in the last year that it's not difficult to achieve at least 20 times that revenue*". As the founder of Company A said: "*we are exchanging ideas with other companies but not here. [...] We live on the global area that you can reach someone by e-mail*".

Conversely, the two cases that pursued a strategy of shift, i.e. Case B and C, are the ones that are mainly focused on growing in terms of employees and a mix of internal

competences, which we can operationalise as "qualitative growth", as the founder of Company B said *"we are in pre-revenue, we are growing in usage"*. Moreover, both Case B and C demonstrated being able to leverage the internal connections with other founders and also investors within UPTEC network, as the manager of Company C said about the other start-ups managers: *"is not that we have projects together, but we certainly help each other when we see an opportunity or when someone needs help"*. Thus, there emerges a prevalence of relational resources that mainly come from proximity.

Figure 1 summarises these results in a matrix of growth and innovation patterns of the studied start-ups in health-related industries.

Fig. 1. Locus of innovation, growth patterns and networking in the start-ups of the study

We can argue that start-ups B and C mainly showed an attitude towards developing a growth path that builds on relational elements. Conversely, Cases A and D demonstrate being more "mature" in raising funds and thus on an idea and business model that are well-recognisable. These two patterns can be compared respectively to the features of "start-ups" and "scale-ups" in the work by Ritter and Pedersen [25]. According to these authors, start-ups are the ones that focus on constant experimentation in the search for a business model, trying different means and developing new capabilities to support changes, like Cases B and C that changed from the driver to the locus of innovation. Scale-ups mainly aim at the replication of the original business model, as it is the locus of innovation for Cases A and D, thus they

focus on quickly onboarding funds and resources to support expansion and business model replication.

5 Conclusions

This study investigated the innovation strategy and growth patterns of start-ups that introduce new products, services or integrated solutions to meet social needs, whose main purpose is to improve health conditions and the well-being of people with advanced technologies and dedicated services. We conducted a multiple case study research by selecting four start-ups incubated in UPTEC, the science and technology park of the University of Porto in Portugal, with the aim of performing a contextualised research.

The findings of the study show that healthcare start-ups follow different growth patterns and ways of leveraging the interconnections of the innovation ecosystem they belong to, according to their innovation strategy. The emerging patterns can inform new ventures in knowledge-intensive industries to develop specific innovative endeavours according to the growth directions they aim for, i.e. a “qualitative” growth aimed at increasing the team in terms of employees and mix of competences, a “quantitative” growth in terms of financial resources, i.e. funds and revenues, or a mix of them. This finding has a practical impact for start-ups since it recommends founders willing to pursue a particular growth goal to focus on specific incubator’s services.

Moreover, these results have important implications also for incubators and innovation intermediaries that support start-ups in health-related industries. Findings in terms of preferred growth patterns, locus of innovation and leveraging of specific services of the incubator may contribute to guiding the development of business development programs targeted at health and well-being start-ups. Further research on investment and development programs targeting the innovator's thinking and attitudes toward growth is requested [9].

The results of the study have important implications also for the field of Healthcare 5.0, where the principles and applications of Industry 4.0 are considered along with the further customisation of care, therapeutics and diagnostics to patients and professionals [2,3]. In this sense, the contributions of start-ups are multifaceted and their innovation paths can be further supported for the sustainability and competitiveness of the health-related industries whether proper policies, strategies and intermediary practices take into account their respective growth directions. Funding opportunities should be also framed accordingly, with the provision of private and public investments and budgetary support for sustainable business models [3], as the ones of the start-ups and scale-ups that show a consolidated growth attitude.

The study has some limitations. First, the number of start-ups analysed is decent, but in order to provide a stronger theoretical contribution, the number of cases should be enriched. Furthermore, since the study focused on Portugal, a comparative analysis could help in understanding also the role of the institutional environment and culture. Finally, albeit several data have been collected, a longitudinal analysis could also unveil growth trajectories. Finally, since some of the cases analysed were incubated during the

covid-19 pandemic, further analyses could also consider its impact on innovation strategies and growth.

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